

RESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: RAUM

FIRST NAME: DOMINIQUE

PROGRAM CODE: PHGH

COURSE CODE: ACA-401D

PERIOD NUMBER: 6

INSTRUCTOR: DR GULMA

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The author applied UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics
 The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:
 The author did not use Zotero to insert references
 The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)
 The author used the following software: MSWord 2019, Grammarly v.1.0.32.485 on Windows 10

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Kate Turabian identified several actions that are at risk of being seen as plagiarism and need referencing. (Select all that apply)¹

- You quote, paraphrase or summarise a source but fail to cite it.
- You use ideas or methods from a source but fail to cite them.
- You use the exact words of a source, and you do cite it but fail to put those words in question marks or in a block quotation
- You paraphrase a source and mention it but paraphrase too closely.

2. When applying the Chicago style of referencing, you may choose to (select all that apply):

Commented [KG1]: The footnote superscript is placed on the correct answer, not the questions. And it is placed after the punctuation!

Commented [KG2]: Be uniform with terminal punctuations. Either all options have or they do not have!

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¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*, Ninth edition, (Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 80.

- Place the author's name, date, and page numbers between parentheses using the author-date type².
- Place the author's name, surname, date and page number between parentheses using the author-date style.
- Use numerical footnotes as a link to the reference in the bibliography.
- Use a shorter format using the name, followed by the source's title and the page references, when reusing a source mentioned before while using the note style³.
3. Which of the following contents are not part of the "prebuild" before the introduction?
- Limitations and delimitations⁴.
- The abstract.
- The copyright.
- Dedications and acknowledgements.
4. When applying the World Health Organization (WHO) style to the bibliography of a research paper, the following rules apply (check the correct answer):
- References are to be listed in order of appearance in the paper.
- Only the first author is to be mentioned. The following ones will be replaced by mentioning "et al."

²Turabian, Kate L., 142.

³Turabian, Kate L., 141-142.

⁴Turabian, Kate L., 67-70.

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When writing technical documents, the author must provide references with a superscript number, with all data given at the bottom of the page in numerical order throughout the piece⁵.

None of the above applies.

5. When using the World Health Organization (WHO) style, quotations (check the correct answer):

Are to be adapted to the spelling and grammar of the English language used (United Kingdom or United States).

Punctuations should be enclosed inside the quotation marks if they are part of the quotation, even if using United States grammar⁶.

Punctuations should always be enclosed inside the quotation marks, even if using United States grammar.

Need to be written in italic and bold format and placed between double quotes.

6. The qualitative research approach should not be used when (check the correct answer):

When explaining a process or behaviour.

When understanding a phenomenon, a case, a behaviour or a situation.

When describing an issue using numerical data⁷.

When collecting participants' stories, retell them to address the research question.

⁵ World Health Organization. *WHO Style Guide*, Second edition (Geneva: World Health Organization, 2013), 36.

⁶ World Health Organization. 51.

⁷ Adu, Philip. 2016. *Writing the methodology chapter of a qualitative study*. YouTube Video. 1'51".

Commented [KG3]: Search for how to reference videos in footnotes and correct this accordingly!

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7. The conclusion of a research paper will include (check the correct answer):
- Final reflections.
 - A conclusion to every finding.
 - A presentation of actionable recommendations.
 - All of the above⁸.**
8. The basics of paper writing at Euclid University include the following rules (check the correct answer):
- Abbreviations should solely be used between parenthesis and are to be avoided in the main text⁹.**
 - Abbreviations can be used as long as there is a list of acronyms and a first usage of the entire word with the abbreviation in parenthesis following.
 - The referencing style (Chicago, WHO or APA) is up to the student but has to be mentioned and be consistent
 - The student has to use in-text referencing in every type of paper.
9. Which of the following is not part of qualitative research? (Check the correct answer).
- Description of data collection methods or tools.
 - Ethical considerations.
 - Issues of trustworthiness.

⁸ Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. 2019. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Incorporated. 679-683.

⁹ Cleenewerck Laurent and Gulma Kabiru. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University. 40.

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Calculation of the plagiarism percentage¹⁰.

10. When proceeding to the analysis, interpretation, and synthesis of findings, the following points need to be respected (check the correct answer):

- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should be ignored.
- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should not be ignored or deleted¹¹.**
- The collected data has to be presented understandably; inconsistent or unexpected data should be deleted.
- The collected data does not have to be presented understandably; but needs to be consistent.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Adu, Philip. 2016. Writing the methodology chapter of a qualitative study. YouTube Video.

Bloomberg, Linda Dale and Marie Volpe. 2019. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Incorporated.

Cleenewerck Laurent and Gulma Kabiru. 2021. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth edition. Bangui: Euclid University.

Turabian, Kate L. 2018. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Ninth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. 9th edition. Chicago; London: The University of Chicago Press.

Commented [KG4]: Recall that the format of bibliography is not the same as that of a reference list. Visit the attached link for guidance on footnotes and bibliography - <https://library.austincc.edu/help/turabian/>

¹⁰ [Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth edition \(Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, Incorporated, 2019\), 435-438.](#)

¹¹ [Ibid. 83-84.](#)

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World Health Organization 2013. WHO style guide, second edition. Geneva: World Health Organization.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.